

- This is a time twin paradox, and is made out of the following components: The circles paired with the squares, the extra of the parallell, and the outcome of the triangle, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired circles with the squares, then parallell, however, if parallell, then triangle, however, if triangle, then paired circles with the squares. This twin paradox explained and shown before produces a conversion switch called the shapes shape reference conversion projection switch, where the reference conversion twin paradox is made of the following components: The degrees paired with the rotations, the extra of the curves, and the outcome of the angles, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired degrees with the rotations, then curves, however, if curves, then angles, however, if angles, then paired degrees with the rotations. This twin paradox explained and shown before gets switched by the projection switch twin paradox, which is made of the following components: The layers paired with the sheets, the extra of the folds, and the outcome of the patterns, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired layers with the sheets, then folds, however, if folds, then patterns, however, if patterns, then paired layers with the sheets. This twin paradox explained and shown before produces the name for the explainer date mirror last final hidden twin paradox, which is the finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally date mirror last final hidden twin paradox. Then, the process of creating the name for the explainer date mirror last final hidden twin paradox proceeds to create 4 twin paradoxes, where the 1st twin paradox is made of the following components: The circles paired with the degrees, the extra of the layers, and the outcome of finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired circles with the degrees, then layers, however, if layers, then finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally, however, if finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally, then paired circles with the degrees. The 2nd twin paradox is made of the following components: The squares paired with the rotations, the extra of the sheets, and the outcome of finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired squares with the rotations, then sheets, however, if sheets, then finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally, however if finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally, then paired squares with the rotations. The 3rd twin paradox is made of the following components: The parallell paired with the curves, the extra of the folds, and the outcome of finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired parallell with the curves, then folds, however, if folds, then finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally, however, if finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally, then paired parallell with the curves. The 4th twin paradox is made of the following

components: The triangle paired with the angles, the extra of the patterns, and the outcome of finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally, where the twin paradox goes as followed: If paired triangles with the angles, then patterns, however, if patterns, then finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally, however, if finally perpetually particularity nano particularity perpetually finally, then paired triangles with the angles.

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